

Near Field Communication Technology: Communication Mechanism and Threats

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Abstract— Near Field Communication is wireless short-distance communication technology. The necessary components in communication are available on low cost and also it is fast in connecting. This paper discusses security threats in NFC and a solution that could be implemented between an RFID tag and a reader to exchange a secret without performing any expensive computation. NFC operates on three modes: Peer-to-Peer, Reader/Writer, and Card Emulation. We have introduced an NFC specific key agreement mechanism, which provides cheap and fast secure key agreement. Key agreement techniques without authentication can be used to provide a standard secure channel. This resistance against Man-in-the-Middle attacks makes NFC an ideal method for secure pairing of devices. The paper describes some key threats applicable to NFC such as eavesdropping, data corruption, data modification, data insertion, and man-in-the-middle-attack and solutions to protect against these threats.

Keywords— Key Agreement, Near Field Communication, Operation Modes, RFID, Threats.

I. INTRODUCTION

NFC is a technology for wireless short-distance communication. It's Point-to-point communication technology. The operational range for NFC is within less than 20 cm. Such short range is good from a security perspective as it diminishes the threat of eavesdropping. Other reasons to use NFC are the low cost of the necessary components and that the connecting time is negligible.

Fig. 1 Using NFC

It is small circuit attached to a small antenna, capable of transmitting data to a distance of several meters to a reader device (reader) in response to a query. Most RFID tags are passive, meaning that they are battery-less, and obtain their power from the query signal. They are already attached to almost anything: clothing, foods, access cards and so on.

It is impossible to give a complete picture of NFC applications as NFC is just an interface. Contactless Token covers most of applications, which use NFC to retrieve some data from a passive token. The passive token could be a contactless Smart Card, an RFID label, or a key fob. In Ticketing / Micro Payment application example, the NFC interface is used to transfer some valuable information. The ticket or the micro payment data is stored in a secure device. This could be a contactless Smart Card, but could as well be a mobile phone.

The features of Near Field Communication includes followings.

- A. *Intuitive*: It's a very easy way to interact between two devices, because a user just need to bring two devices together and it's done .
- B. *Interoperable*: NFC works with existing contactless card technologies, existing RFID tags and contactless smartcards .
- C. *Ready secure*: Data transmission range is short, due to that when devices get out of that short range communication automatically terminates. This shows that it's inherently secured.

It is also compatible with the global contactless standards (ISO 14443 and/or ISO 18092), which means agencies that have already deployed contactless programs enjoy a built-in advantage, as their equipment may readily interact with NFC- enabled mobile devices and provide richer services. Like RFID, NFC is a versatile and innovative technology and certainly not limited to mobile payments. NFC may be heavily deployed in a short time to come, as its applications are already undergoing large scale tests in Europe, North America, Asia and Oceania. Test examples are public transport payment, credit cards, electronic tickets, advertisement and W-LAN set up. The NFC development is focused by the NFC Forum, an organization of over 200 companies working together to promote NFC.

The devices in the communication share a single RF band in which the communication is half-duplex. When one device is transmitting, the other one has to listen first and should start to transmit after the first one finishes. One of the features of NFC technology is that mobile devices can be used both as information storage or an NFC reader. They can read information from NFC tags and also display that information on the screen with an ability to make additional processing. Also it can be used as a digital storage, e.g., storing credit card information, storing URL of website etc.

II. NFC OPERATION MODES

As per NFC forum (www.nfc-forum.org/home), there are three operating modes; Peer-to-Peer, Reader/Writer, and Card Emulation.

A. *Peer-to-Peer Mode*

In the peer-to-peer mode, two devices can exchange data at link-level. This mode is standardized on the ISO/IEC 18092 (formerly ECMA 340) standard, and allows data speed up to 424 Kbit/s. Examples of such mode are,

- File Transfer
- Transfer of Business Card (contact transfer)

Fig. 2 Peer-to-peer mode of operation

B. Reader/Writer Mode

In the reader/writer mode, NFC devices can read and write data from/to NFC tags. In this mode NFC mobile acts as an initiator and passive tag acts as target. Here tag does not need any power. The initiator device generates radio signals and the target device gets powered by this electromagnetic field. The target device responds to the initiator by modulating the existing electromagnetic field. So NFC tag does not need a battery to work. It takes power from initiator device using load modulation technique. Examples are,

- Smart-poster
- Mobile Healthcare (ECMA-340)
- Social networking
- Vehicle information system

C. Card Emulation Mode

In the card emulation mode, NFC device acts as an RFID card and other NFC devices can read data from this NFC device. Stored information in the NFC device is used for further operations. Examples are,

- Payment
- Access control systems.
- Coupons
- E-ticketing
- Electronic Voting

III. OPERATION OF NFC

This kind of communication also named as inductive coupled system. The RFID reader generated magnetic field by passing the current through its coil. If a tag comes under the range of this magnetic field, the current passes to tag. So the electric voltage is reform and coupled to capacitor of tag. In figure 3, we can clearly see the capacitor gets charged and will power the chip for operation.

Fig. 3 Power the chip for operation

Near-field RFID system conveys data back using load modulation technique. The voltage generated by inductive coupling in tag, so current into the coil will give grow to own small magnetic field. This magnetic field will oppose the reader's field. Reader will also detect some extra current flow through its coil and this additional current in reader's coil is proportional to the load across the tag's coil, so it's called load modulation. The idea of load modulation is depicted in figure 4. So that means tag can send some encoded signal to RFID reader and reader can easily detect as similar to variation in a current. This technique depends upon the number of bits transmitted, data rate and required redundancy. The operation of system depends upon frequency of operation and radiated energy.

Fig. 4 Load modulation technique

IV. ACTIVE AND PASSIVE TAGS

Finally there are only two types of tag which are compatible to RFID, active and passive tag.

A. Active tag

Active tags need a power supply for the operation. Power supply can be provided with inbuilt battery backup source. Due that reason their life time is also less. They can be particularly useful for goods which need to be tracked from long distances like cargo.

B. Passive tag

Passive tag does not need any battery backup power. They induce energy from the reader itself, which is reason for long life tag. So it does effect on footprint of tag, which make it small parcel.

V. NFC THREATS

The contactless token systems may emerge as one of the most pervasive computing technologies; there are still a huge number of problems that need to be solved before their massive deployment.

One of the fundamental issues still to be addressed is privacy. The products labelled with tags reveal sensitive information when queried by readers, and they do it indiscriminately. A problem closely related to privacy is tracking, or violations of location privacy. This is possible because the answers provided by tags are usually predictable: in fact, most of the times, tags provide always the same identifier, which will allow a third party to easily establish an association between a given tag and its holder or owner. Even in the case in which tags try not to reveal any kind of valuable information that could be used to identify themselves or their holder, there are many situations where, by using an assembly of tags (constellation), this tracking will still be possible. Although the two aforementioned problems are the most important security questions that arise from NFC technology, there are some others worth to mention:

A. *Eavesdropping*

Because NFC is a wireless communication interface it is obvious that eavesdropping is an important issue. When two devices communicate via NFC they use RF waves to talk to each other. An attacker can of course use an antenna to also receive the transmitted signals. Either by experimenting or by literature research the attacker can have the required knowledge on how to extract the transmitted data out of the received RF signal. Also the equipment required to receive the RF signal as well as the equipment to decode the RF signal must be assumed to be available to an attacker as there is no special equipment necessary.

The NFC communication is usually done between two devices in close proximity. This means they are not more than 10 cm (typically less) away from each other. The main question is how close an attacker needs to be to be able to retrieve a usable RF signal. Unfortunately, there is no correct answer to this question. The reason for that is the huge number of parameters which determine the answer. For example the distance depends on the following parameters, and there are many more.

- RF field characteristic of the given sender device (i.e. antenna geometry, shielding effect of the case, the PCB, the environment)
- Characteristic of the attacker's antenna (i.e. antenna geometry, possibility to change the position in all 3 dimensions)
- Quality of the attacker's receiver
- Quality of the attacker's RF signal decoder
- Setup of the location where the attack is performed (e.g. barriers like walls or metal, noise floor level)
- Power sent out by the NFC device

Therefore any exact number given would only be valid for a certain set of the above given parameters and cannot be used to derive general security guidelines.

B. *Data Corruption*

Instead of just listening an attacker can also try to modify the data which is transmitted via the NFC interface. In the simplest case the attacker just wants to disturb the communication such that the receiver is not able to understand the data sent by the other device.

Data corruption can be achieved by transmitting valid frequencies of the data spectrum at a correct time. The correct time can be calculated if the attacker has a good understanding of the used modulation scheme and coding. This attack is not too complicated, but it does not allow the attacker to manipulate the actual data. It is basically a Denial of Service attack.

C. Data Modification

In data modification the attacker wants the receiving device to actually receive some valid, but manipulated data. This is very different from just data corruption. The feasibility of this attack highly depends on the applied strength of the amplitude modulation. This is because the decoding of the signal is different for 100% and 10% modulation.

In 100% modulation the decoder basically checks the two half bits for RF signal on (no pause) or RF signal off (pause). In order to make the decoder understand a one as a zero or vice versa, the attacker must do two things. First, a pause in the modulation must be filled up with the carrier frequency. This is feasible. But, secondly, the attacker must generate a pause of the RF signal, which is received by the legitimate receiver. This means the attacker must send out some RF signal such that this signal perfectly overlaps with the original signal at the receiver's antenna to give a zero signal at the receiver. This is practically impossible. However, due to the modified Miller coding in the case of two subsequent ones, the attacker can change the second one into a zero, by filling the pause which encodes the second one. The decoder would then see no pause in the second bit and would decode this as a correct zero, because it is preceded by a one. In 100% modulation an attacker can therefore never change a bit of value 0 to a bit of value 1, but an attacker can change a bit of value 1 to a bit of value 0, in case this bit is preceded by a bit of value 1 (i.e. with a probability of 0.5).

In 10% modulation the decoder measures both signal levels (82% and Full) and compares them. In case they are in the correct range the signal is valid and gets decoded. An attacker could try to add a signal to the 82% signal, such that the 82% signal appears as the Full signal and the actual Full signal becomes the 82% signal. This way the decoder would decode a valid bit of the opposite value of the bit sent by the correct sender. Whether the attack is feasible depends a lot on the dynamic input range of the receiver. It is very likely that the much higher signal level of the modified signal would exceed the possible input range, but for certain situations this cannot be ruled out completely.

The conclusion is that for the modified Miller encoding with 100% ASK this attack is feasible for certain bits and impossible for other bits, but for Manchester coding with 10% ASK this attack is feasible on all bits.

D. Data Insertion

This means that the attacker inserts messages into the data exchange between two devices. But this is only possible, in case the answering device needs a very long time to answer. The attacker could then send his data earlier than the valid receiver. The insertion will be successful, only, if the inserted data can be transmitted, before the original device starts with the answer. If both data streams overlap, the data will be corrupted.

E. Man-in-the-Middle-Attack

In the classical Man-in-the-Middle Attack, two parties which want to talk to each other, called Alice and Bob, are tricked into a three party conversation by an attacker Eve.

Fig. 5 Man-in-the-Middle-Attack

Alice and Bob must not be aware of the fact that they are not talking to each other, but that they are both sending and receiving data from Eve. Such a setup is the classical threat in unauthenticated key agreement protocols like Diffie-Hellmann protocol. Alice and Bob want to agree on a secret key, which they then use for a secure channel. However, as Eve is in the middle, it is possible for Eve to establish a key with Alice and another key with Bob. When Alice and Bob later use their key to secure data, Eve is able to eavesdrop on the communication and also to manipulate data being transferred.

How would that work when the link between Alice and Bob is an NFC link? Assuming that Alice uses active mode and Bob would be in passive mode, we have the following situation. Alice generates the RF field and sends data to Bob. In case Eve is close enough, she can eavesdrop the data sent by Alice. Additionally she must actively disturb the transmission of Alice to make sure that Bob doesn't receive the data. This is possible for Eve, but this can also be detected by Alice. In case Alice detects the disturbance, Alice can stop the key agreement protocol. Let's assume Alice does not check for active disturbance and so the protocol can continue. In the next step Eve needs to send data to Bob. That's already a problem, because the RF field generated by Alice is still there, so Eve has to generate a second RF field. This however, causes two RF fields to be active at the same time. It is practically impossible to perfectly align these two RF fields. Thus, it is practically impossible for Bob to understand data sent by Eve. Because of this and the possibility of Alice to detect the attack much earlier we conclude that in this setup a Man-in-the-Middle attack is practically impossible.

The only other possible setup is that Alice uses active mode and Bob uses active mode, too. In this case Alice sends some data to Bob. Eve can listen and Eve again must disturb the transmission of Alice to make sure that Bob does not receive the data. At this point Alice could already detect the disturbance done by Eve and stop the protocol. Again, let us assume that Alice does not do this check and the protocol continues. In the next step Eve would need to send data to Bob. At first sight this looks better now, because of the active-active communication Alice has turned off the RF field. Now Eve turns on the RF field and can send the data. The problem here now is that also Alice is listening as she is expecting an answer from Bob. Instead she will receive the data sent by Eve and can again detect a problem in the protocol and stop the protocol. It is impossible in this setup for Eve to send data either to Alice or Bob and making sure that this data is not received by Bob or Alice, respectively.

We claim that due to the above given reasons it is practically infeasible to mount a Man-in-the-Middle attack in a real-world scenario.

VI. CONCLUSION

NFC is a technology for wireless short-distance communication. It's Point-to-point communication technology. It is small circuit attached to a small antenna, capable of transmitting data to a distance of several meters to a reader device (reader) in response to a query. In this paper, we have discussed features of Near Field Communication, mechanism of communication, operation modes and some threats. Features of Near Field Communication include Intuitive, Interoperable and Ready Secure. NFC operation modes can be peer to peer, Reader/Writer and Card Emulation. Two types of tags compatible with RFID are active and passive tags. Privacy is primary issue that needs to be addressed in NFC. A problem closely related to privacy is tracking, or violations of location privacy. The major threats associated with Near Field Communication are eavesdropping, data corruption, data modification, data insertion, and man-in-the-middle-attack.

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